

Crime against Women and Role of Tripura Police

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Abstract: The issue of crime against women is one of the most important issues of concern in the 21st century. Rights of women are violated in different ways. Most alarming is that the women become victims of violence by their husbands or intimate partners also. Though, the rate of crime against women is less in north-eastern states than the national level, but the condition of women is not better off both in matrilineal and patrilineal societies in north-east India. The stereotype assigning of social roles on the basis of gender makes women inferior in the society and in turn contribute to increasing trend of crime against them. In this backdrop the present paper focuses on the rate of crime in north eastern states more specifically in Tripura and the role of Tripura police in this regard.

Key words: Crime against women, Rights, Violence against women

Introduction

Women's Rights is the most concerning issue of contemporary time. Women constitute half of the world's population and are entitled to equal and inalienable rights, equal to their male counterparts. In all most all the states women are legally entitled to socio-economic-political rights without any discrimination. The term 'legally' is most important here. The term 'Women's Rights' itself indicates that though 'legally' women are entitled to rights but in practice they are not often. In all societies, whether patrilineal or matrilineal, women are deprived of their basic rights. Their rights are violated because of crimes. Now-a-days, most of the crimes against women are heinous. This is not only alarming but derogatory for the society as a whole. India is also not different from this. Crime against women at national level is a matter of deep concern and so is the case of Northeastern states also in particular.

Northeastern part of India comprises of eight states viz. Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Nagaland, Mizoram, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tripura and Sikkim (Bhattacharjee, 1999). Among these eight states, only Meghalaya is matrilineal. But, in case of crime against women, whether matrilineal or patrilineal, women of all states face the similar nature of violation of their rights. Tripura is the smallest state of Northeast India; it is

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basically a patrilineal society and there exist number of incidents, which show that violation of the rights of women is in existence in Tripura.

Objectives:

The present study focuses on the following objectives:

1. To study the nature of crime against women in Northeast India with special reference to Tripura.
2. To study the present situation of crime against women in Tripura.

Methodology:

This paper has been prepared based on secondary data collected from internet sources available on government official websites. Data have been analysed to fulfil the objectives of the present study. Through analysis the research questions have also been answered.

Crime Against Women:

As already discussed, crime against women is a major issue of concern in the present day. It creates barrier for ensuring equality, development and rights of women. The goal of sustainable development that “leave no one behind” cannot be achieved without ensuring a violence free society for women. Social values too are responsible for crimes against women. The social stratification keeps women far behind of men. The idea is that women are too weak to deal with the different issues outside the family. Social values assign the functions of home to women. Since childhood boys and girls are reared with the idea that household works are meant for girls and outside works for boys. This social connotation develops an idea among both male and female that the girls can’t do any out-side works. Naturally, after being economically independent there are women who remain dependent upon the male members of the family. This also contributes many times for rising of crime against women in the society. In Indian society crime by the initiate partners or by the family members against the women is a matter of great concern now-a-days (Roy Karmakar, 2011)

According to CAG report “Crime against women includes any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life” (CAG Report, Crime Against Women).

As per UN, violence against women is "any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual, or mental harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life." (WHO)

Thus, any act that causes physical or psychological harm to women can be referred as crime against women.

Table 1: Crime against Women in India

Crime Head	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Rape	9%	9%	8%	8%	7%	7%
Kidnapping & Abduction	18%	19%	18%	17%	18%	19%
Cruelty by Husband and Relatives	29%	27%	31%	30%	32%	31%
Assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty	24%	24%	22%	23%	21%	19%
Insult to the modesty of women	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%
Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%
Others	15%	16%	17%	18%	17%	19%
Total Crime Against Women	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Source: Government of India Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. Women & Men in India 2024

Data in the Table 1 shows that since 2017 to 2022, though minimal, but there is a decreasing trend of rape in India. It was 9% in 2017 and 2018, 8% in 2019 and 2020, 7% in 2021 and 2022. There was not much difference in cases of Kidnapping and Abduction since 2017 to 2022. There was also a decreasing trend in the number of cases related to assault on women. The data show that the cases of assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty registered in the year 2017 and 2018 was 24%, whereas 22%, 23%, 21% and 19% was in the year 2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022 respectively. The number of cases registered of insult to the modesty of women was 2% in each year from 2017 to 2022. The same trend shows that the total number of cases registered under Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 was 3% in each year since 2017 to 2022.

But most alarming fact is that the increasing number of cases of crime against women done by the husbands and relatives in India. Data shows that the number of cases registered of cruelty by husband and relatives was 29% in 2017, 27% in 2018, 31% in 2019, 30% in 2020, 32% in 2021 and 31% in 2022. Crime against

women by the intimate partners and relatives are gradually increasing in India. It is extremely alarming that not in the outside but women are not safe in their own home itself.

Table 2: Rate of Total Crime against Women in NE India

State	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Arunachal Pradesh	58.7	53.4	51.1	43.3	38.0	49.1	44.4	42.8
Assam	131.3	143.6	166.0	177.8	154.3	168.3	81.2	68.6
Meghalaya	27.0	40.7	35.7	34.6	34.9	41.7	41.6	37.5
Mizoram	23.2	57.6	42.2	28.7	28.8	29.1	24.1	29.9
Nagaland	9.2	6.9	7.3	4.1	3.7	5.1	4.6	5.2
Manipur	19.6	18.1	17.7	17.2	15.8	19.1	15.6	12.5
Sikkim	50.3	53.1	55.5	39.8	44.2	40.6	55.4	41.0
Tripura	53.9	51.2	46.5	54.5	44.0	40.2	37.1	38.7

(Crime rate indicates as per one lakh)

Source: Official Website of National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB)

Table 2 shows the rate of total crime against women in North-eastern India. In Arunachal Pradesh the rate of crime against women was 58.7, 53.4, 51.1, 43.3, 38.0, 49.1, 44.4 and 42.8 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 respectively. The condition of Assam is the worse than any other state of northeastern India. In Assam, the rate shows that it was 131.3, 143.6, 166.0, 177.8, 154.3, 168.3, 81.2, 68.6 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 respectively. Though, there was a decreasing trend in the recent years of the crime against women but still it alarming. In Mizoram, it was 23.2, 57.6, 42.2, 28.7, 28.8, 29.1, 24.1, 29.9 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 respectively. In 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 the rate of number of cases of crime against women in Nagaland was 9.2, 6.9, 7.3, 4.1, 3.7, 5.1, 4.6, 5.2 respectively. It is really encouraging that the crime rate particularly against women is very low in Nagaland. It shows, the respect for women that the society bears. In Manipur, it was 19.6, 18.1, 17.7, 17.2, 15.8, 19.1, 15.6 and 12.5 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 respectively. Manipur is the place of 'Meira Paibi', the torch bearers. The smaller number of rates of crime against women in Manipur shows that the rights of women are protected to some extent than other states of India. In Sikkim, the rate of crime against women was 50.3, 53.1, 55.5, 39.8, 44.2, 40.6, 55.4, 41.0 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 respectively. Meghalaya is the only matrilineal state in Northeastern India. In spite of that, the women of

the state are victims of violence. The rate of crime against women in a matrilineal society like Meghalaya is not less. As per the data, the rate of crime against women in Meghalaya was 27.0, 40.7, 35.7, 34.6, 34.9, 41.7, 41.6, 37.5 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 respectively.

Table 2 shows that the rate of crime against women in Tripura was 53.9, 51.2, 46.5, 54.5, 44.0, 40.2, 37.1, 38.7 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 203 respectively. It is encouraging that there is a trend of gradual decreasing of rate of crime against women in the state. It was more than 50 in the year 2016, 2017 even in the year 2019, but in the year 2022 and 2023 it was 37.1 and 38.7.

It is important to mention here that the national rate of crime against women since 2016 to 2023 was more than 60. In this respect, the condition of Northeastern states is better. But initiative needs to be taken to decrease the number more in these states also.

Crime against women in Tripura:

Tripura is the second smallest state of Northeastern region. At present the state has the total population of approximately 42 lakhs. Among them, approximately 49% are female. Tripura is one of the most literate states of India. But, in spite of higher literacy rate the females of the state suffer from the violation of their rights. Crime against women is a major issue of the state. As per NCRB reports, the Tripura was one of the top state in terms of crime against women. But, since 2020 there was a gradual decrease in the rate of crime against women. Rights of women are violated due to rape, abduction, kidnapping, domestic violence, dowry deaths etc. in Tripura.

Table 3: Charge sheeting Rate in cases related to Crime against Women

State	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Arunachal Pradesh	68.3	76.7	72.0	71.9	72.5	77.6	76.6	71.4
Assam	58	65.0	57.7	57.2	63.8	52.9	41.4	65.2
Meghalaya	61.6	82.9	79.4	72.1	66.0	76.1	71.6	75.0
Mizoram	97.5	96.7	96.4	97.0	98.8	94.9	98.0	97.8
Nagaland	59.8	77.2	64.6	58.1	67.6	80.4	92.2	76.5
Manipur	65.7	55.0	28.7	44.8	56.1	48.4	65.1	69.6
Sikkim	90.4	75.5	93.0	88.0	91.4	98.3	75.0	76.6
Tripura	80.9	86.9	80.9	85.4	82.5	84.7	87.3	89.6

(Crime rate indicates as per one lakh) Source: NCRB Website

The role of police is crucial to stop crime in any state. More crucial is to submit charge sheets in cases of crime. It is important for both victims and accused. Delay in submitting charge sheets shows the ineffective and inefficient role of police, ultimately leads to violation of rights of both victims and accused. Table 3, reflects the data related to the role of police in producing charge sheeting in cases related to women. In Tripura, there is a gradual increase of charge sheeting by the police in cases of crime against women. It was 80.9, 86.9, 80.9, 85.4, 82.5, 84.7, 87.3 and 89.6 in the year 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 respectively. Thus, the table shows that in the year 2016, the rate of charge sheeting was 80.9 whereas in 2022 and 2023 it was 87.3 and 89.6 respectively. This gradual increase indicates the increasing level of efficiency of police personnel in terms of their role in Tripura.

Major Findings:

From the study it has found that:

1. Different types of crime take place against women in India, such as, rape, kidnapping, insult of modesty, crimes for dowry. But most of the crime are committed by the intimate partners or husbands or family members.
2. Crimes committed by husbands or family members causes serious concern for the protection of women. State can't intervene in the family matters unless the victim approached for redress.
3. There is a decreasing trend of rate of crime against women in the north-eastern states. Though, these states are also not free from crime against women. However, the rate of crime against women in the north-eastern states are less than the national rate.
4. There is a decreasing trend of crime against women Tripura since 2017.
5. Though, there is a decreasing trend of crime against women in Tripura, but it still exists. But, the most important fact is the efficient role played by the police. The rate of charge sheeting of cases is increasing which ensures the protection of rights of both victims and accused.

Conclusion:

The role of police in Tripura has been developed because of the use of technology. Installation CCTV in different parts as well as prompt action in cases particularly in heinous crimes is appreciable. However, Tripura is a state of higher literacy rate. More positive steps need to be taken by the police to decrease the rate of crime in the state. There are other north eastern state where the condition of women is better off. Governmental policies, social awareness, increasing level of women education are contributing for the overall development of women in the state. Participation of women in decision making process, role of

women self-help groups, government policy of 'Lakhpati Didi' ensures empowerment. Women empowerment, women education and social awareness ultimately contribute to minimise the rate of crime against women.

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